

Results from the Magnetic Suspension Mass Comparator for Vacuum-to-Air Mass Dissemination

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Abstract — Experiments to realize the new definition of the kilogram will be carried out in vacuum. NIST has developed a magnetic suspension mass comparator to disseminate the new definition to air. This paper details the current status of the system. This includes results from recent work to characterize and improve the performance of the magnetic suspension portion of the system. A general overview of the system, as well as key results are given.

Index Terms — metrology, magnetic levitation, electromagnetic modeling, calibration, and interferometry.

I. INTRODUCTION

The SI unit of mass, the kilogram, is expected to be redefined in 2018 such that its magnitude is set by fixing the value of the Planck constant [1]. This new realization represents not only an entirely new way to realize the unit of mass but also presents new challenges for its dissemination. The primary realization of the kilogram, under the new definition, will take place in either a watt balance or through an X-ray crystal diffraction [2] experiment. Both experiments occur in a vacuum environment, a striking change from the current definition and dissemination process that takes place in air. While the general process of mass dissemination will remain largely the same, a reliable method of vacuum-to-air mass transfer is needed.

The current method for vacuum-to-air mass comparison involves empirical models developed using sorption standards to account for mass changes that air introduces when a mass is removed from vacuum [3]. At the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) an alternative approach is being pursued where the standard artifact, kept in vacuum, is directly compared to a test mass in air [4]. The mass comparison is carried out by coupling the mass comparator located in a vacuum chamber to a mass located in a chamber at atmospheric pressure through a magnetic suspension method [5]. This approach eliminates the need to make corrections to account for environmental sorption effects.

Over the course of the last year we have carried out two lines of work on the magnetic suspension mass comparator (MSMC). In the first, we finished a redesign and build of the 2nd generation MSMC. In the second, we carried out research on a prototype MSMC to characterize the performance of the magnetic suspension and identify key areas where the

performance and stability of the suspension could be improved. In this paper, we discuss both of these works.

II. MAGNETIC SUSPENSION SYSTEM

A schematic of the magnetic suspension mass comparator that will be used in the final system is shown in Figure 1. The two chambers are made of aluminum. A precision mass comparator (readability of 10 μg) is set in the evacuated upper chamber; its mass pan and the upper magnet assembly are hung from the comparator. The upper magnet assembly consists of a rare-earth cylinder magnet with a soft-iron cylinder placed above it; the soft-iron serves to enhance the field. A multi-turn coil is wrapped around the permanent magnet and soft-iron. Two layers of magnetic shielding surround the coil to reduce the spatial extent of the magnet's field and limit its interaction with any surrounding magnetic materials. The lower chamber contains a second magnet assembly with a mass plate connected below it and is held at atmospheric pressure. The lower magnet assembly is similar to the upper *sans* coil. A Hall sensor is embedded in the flange separating the upper and lower chambers. Not shown is the interferometer, set below the lower assembly, which provides higher precision tracking of the vertical motion of the suspended assembly.

A. Mass Comparison Measurement

A typical mass comparison using the MSMC is performed as follows. A reference mass, calibrated using the watt balance, is placed on the mass pan positioned above the upper magnet assembly in the upper chamber. The lower magnet assembly, *sans* test mass, is then magnetically suspended and a mass reading is taken. Next, the magnetic suspension is turned off. The reference mass is removed from the upper pan and a test mass is placed on the lower pan. Then, the lower assembly is re-suspended and a measurement of the test mass is made. The magnitude of the test mass is that of the calibrated mass of the standard plus the difference in the two mass measurements. Additional corrections are made to account for the gravitational change due to the differing heights of the measured masses and the affect of air buoyancy on the lower mass.

B. Magnetic Suspension Operation

In the newly built MSMC attention was paid to factors that could influence performance, as well as user interaction with

Figure 1: Schematic of the final MSMC. The precision mass comparator is placed under vacuum in an aluminum chamber. Support beams connect the load cell to mass pan which can be loaded and unloaded with different masses kept under vacuum. Connected to the bottom of the support beams is the upper magnet assembly which includes a coil for feedback. In the lower aluminum chamber, typically held at atmospheric pressure, is the lower magnet assembly and mass pan which can also have masses loaded and unloaded. Separating the two chambers is a flange with an embedded Hall sensor used for detecting the motion of the suspended lower assembly.

the system. Perhaps the most important factor of all is the stability of the magnetically suspended lower assembly. Vertical motion of the lower assembly is interpreted as a force by the mass comparator, that in turn can lead to errors in the mass measurement. To combat this, a large portion of the work over that past year has focused on characterizing the feedback system and identifying improvements.

The magnetic suspension works as follows. A Hall sensor placed between the two magnets monitors changes in the local magnetic field related to motion of the suspended assembly [6]. That signal is passed to an analog-to-digital converter and then fed to a field programmable gate array (FPGA). The switch to an FPGA over the course of the last year has provided a significant overall improvement in performance. A feedback scheme using a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) loop is implemented on the FPGA. The output voltage of the FPGA is applied across the coil housed in the upper assembly and controls the magnetic force produced by the coil. In this way changes in the gap distances between the two assemblies are minimized. The system is operated so that minimal current is needed. The separation gap is adjusted

depending on whether or not the test mass is added to the lower assembly.

C. Results

To evaluate the stability of the system we used the prototype MSMC and a mass comparator with a readability of $100\ \mu\text{g}$. The mass reading was monitored while a 1 kg artifact was suspended from the lower magnetic assembly. Under such conditions we achieved mass readings with uncertainties at the $100\ \mu\text{g}$ level, the noise floor of the comparator used in the test setup. Additionally, the vertical fluctuations were below $200\ \text{nm}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$, a reading below the noise floor of our Hall sensor. The real MSMC has recently been completed and similar tests on its performance are underway.

III. CONCLUSION

NIST is currently developing a *mise-en-pratique*, a set of instructions for defining and disseminating a unit that ensures it can be realized at the highest level of precision, for the kilogram. A key component of this is the comparison of a mass standard in vacuum to a test mass in air [7]. Recent efforts have been focused on the magnetic suspension mass comparator to achieve this comparison. Our goal is to carry out mass comparison measurements with a standard uncertainty of less than 20×10^{-9} kg for a 1 kg mass. The current results from the prototype MSMC, along with the newly completed construction of the final MSMC, strongly position us to achieve this goal and provide a new and reliable method to perform vacuum-to-air mass dissemination.

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